

Heats of Mixing of Binary Mixture of Hard Sphere Fluids

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Thermodynamic data for binary liquid mixtures : benzene + carbontetrachloride, cyclohexane + carbontetrachloride, cyclohexane + benzene, cyclohexane + n-hexane, n-hexane + benzene etc. should be quite useful for testing theories of solutions of non-electrolytes since the component liquids are composed of molecules which are relatively simple in shape and structure and can be prepared in good purity. Again, on one hand it enables engineers and chemists to obtain reliable data for design purposes and on the other hand it provides physicists with information on the relation between the macroscopic properties of a mixture and the characteristics of its constituent molecules. However, data for the thermodynamic functions of these systems from fundamental considerations are rare and do not allow the study of phase behaviour.

Recently¹, relations were formulated for calculation of excess thermodynamic functions of binary mixtures of polar-non-polar liquids but here the system is specific for benzene and acetonitrile mixture. Yosim^{2,3} used the results of scale particle theory to calculate the heat of vaporisation of pure liquids and the excess entropy of binary solutions. Huggins⁴ used the results of heat of vaporisation data to calculate heat of mixing of non-ionic binary solutions. The present communication reports an extension of the theory of thermodynamic properties of solutions of non-ionic liquids, previously deduced⁴.

Theoretical :

In this work Huggin's model⁴ is used. Let the types of segments be designated as i, j etc. and the types of segment-segment contact by subscripts ii, ij, jj, etc. Let the average intermolecularly contacting surface area per mole of a single segment of i or j type be designated as a_i^0 or a_j^0 etc. and the average attraction energies per unit contact area as ϵ_{ii} , ϵ_{ij} , ϵ_{jj} etc. If, in a given system, there is only one type of segment, hence only one type of contact, then total intermolecular energy (cohesive energy) per mole is given by

$$E_x = n_x a_x^0 \epsilon_{xx} / 2 \quad (1)$$

$\lambda = i, j, \text{ etc.}$

where, n_x is the number of i or j type of segments per molecule.

The expression⁴ for heat of mixing is

$$H^E = \frac{a_1^0 \Delta \epsilon}{2} \left[\frac{r(x_2 - x_2^2)}{1 + x_2(r-1)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where, $\Delta \epsilon$ is the attraction energy of the binary mixture and is given by

$$\Delta \epsilon = 2\epsilon_{ij} - \epsilon_i - \epsilon_j \quad (3)$$

$$r = a_j^0 / a_i^0 \quad (4)$$

and x_2 is the mole-fraction of one of the components

Results and Discussion

The parameters required for pure components are listed in Table 1. The values of cohesive energies⁵ have been calculated from surface tension of pure liquids. The systems

TABLE 1—PARAMETERS FOR PURE COMPONENTS AT 25°

Component	γ^s dyne cm ⁻¹	σ^s Å	ϵ/k K	E kcal mol ⁻¹
CCl ₄	25.5	5.18	497 ^b	7.18
C ₆ H ₆	27.5	5.02	308 ^c	6.81
c-C ₆ H ₁₂	27.3	5.33	313 ^c	6.21
n-C ₆ H ₁₄	17.4	5.51	413 ^d	6.35

^aRef 8 ^bRef 6 ^cRef 9 ^dRef 7

Fig 1 Plot of heats of mixing (H^E) vs mole fraction (x_2) for the five binary mixtures (1) C₆H₆ + c-C₆H₁₂, (2) C₆H₆ + n-C₆H₁₄, (3) n-C₆H₁₄ + c-C₆H₁₂, (4) c-C₆H₁₂ + CCl₄ and (5) C₆H₆ + CCl₄

we have studied are composed of small and approximately spherical molecules. Therefore, Lennard-Jones potential may be applicable in representing the molecular interactions of the components of the mixture. The Lennard-Jones parameters for the interaction between unlike molecular species are given by the Lorentz-Bertholet⁶ combining rule,

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\epsilon_i \epsilon_j} \quad (5)$$

ϵ_{ij} is the depth of the potential energy curve for a system. The above relation holds good for gaseous states which follows Lennard-Jones type of potential. But in the case of liquids the interaction between the molecules are not as simple as in gaseous state. So when the two fluids are mixed the depth of the potential of the mixture is different from the relation (5). The interaction between the molecules i, j are to be studied in detail on the basis of quantum mechanics to establish the relation. So the following ad hoc relation is proposed,

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\epsilon_i \epsilon_j} (1 + \beta) \quad (6)$$

here β is an adjustable parameter which has been allowed to vary $\pm 5\%$. To obtain satisfactory results for different systems, the approximate values of β are given in Table 2 and the heats of mixing for equimolar mixture are listed in

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS FOR DIFFERENT MIXTURES

System	r	β	$a_1^0 \Delta \epsilon$
$C_6H_6 + CCl_4$	1.53	0.037	0.1706
$c-C_6H_{12} + CCl_4$	1.37	0.037	0.2500
$C_6H_6 + c-C_6H_{12}$	1.131	0.05	1.2127
$C_6H_6 + n-C_6H_{14}$	1.44	0.05	0.8580
$n-C_6H_{14} + c-C_6H_{12}$	1.29	0.027	0.3823

Table 3. For each system A, B and C, three sets of data are given which represent respectively the heats of mixing calculated from equation (2), calculated by Huggin's and ex-

TABLE 3—HEATS OF MIXING AT 25°

System	$H^E, X_2 = 0.5$ cal mol ⁻¹		
	A	B	C
$C_6H_6 + CCl_4$	27.2	27.4	27.0
$c-C_6H_{12} + CCl_4$	35.05	35.1	35.0
$C_6H_6 + c-C_6H_{12}$	184.1	185.7	195 ± 5
$C_6H_6 + n-C_6H_{14}$	128.0	—	205.0
$n-C_6H_{14} + c-C_6H_{12}$	52.8	—	51 ± 1

perimental data⁷. The calculated heats of mixing have been plotted as a function of mole-fraction (x_2) in Fig. 1. The curves satisfy the experimental results qualitatively and also quantitatively.

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